

D6.1

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Abstract

This deliverable provides a summary of the findings and main challenges encountered in WP6.

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Abbreviations

IP	Intellectual Property
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
EIP	Ethereum Improvement Proposal
CC	Creative Commons
DSA	Digital Services Act
DGA	Digital Governance Act
CDSM	Directive on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
T&C	Terms and Conditions
ERC	Ethereum Request for Comment

Introduction

The rapid growth of Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs), unique and non-divisible cryptographic tokens on the blockchain¹, has prompted extensive debate over their legal status and potential applications. Technological proponents often present NFTs as revolutionary tools for enabling digital ownership and rights management.² However, the analysis conducted under the Dafne+ project has revealed substantial legal complexities that affect not only the operation of the Dafne+ platform but also the broader NFT market. The central challenge identified lies in the fundamental legal distinction between the NFT itself, as a cryptographic token, its linked digital asset, and any associated intellectual property (IP) rights. This separation ultimately complicates issues of ownership, licensing, and compliance with existing legal frameworks.

Copyright Implications

Ownership of an NFT does not in itself confer ownership of the underlying digital work or any associated IP rights.³ Acts such as minting, advertising, or selling NFTs may constitute copyright-relevant acts that, if performed without the rights holder's authorisation, may amount to copyright infringement.⁴ Furthermore, NFTs cannot guarantee authenticity, attribution, or scarcity of the linked works, thereby failing to secure “digital ownership”.⁵ This undermines their purported potential to transform creative and cultural markets.

A review of the terms and conditions (T&Cs) of major NFT marketplaces revealed widespread ambiguity and lack of standardisation concerning digital ownership, copyright, and licensing.⁶ Marketplaces frequently employ imprecise language suggesting that buyers acquire ownership of the digital work itself, while crucial terms are often buried in lengthy T&Cs. This lack of clarity increases legal uncertainty for creators, buyers, and marketplace operators. To address these issues, the nature of NFT ownership and the rights acquired by buyers should be clearly and precisely defined and communicated by marketplace operators. Relevant terms should be easily accessible, prominently signposted, and presented in language suitable for non-legal audiences. Moreover, greater standardisation of licensing and ownership terms across platforms should be sought, promoting interoperability and enhancing legal certainty and compliance for all stakeholders.

NFT Licensing

Licensing, essential in enabling compliant work-flows for users, emerged as a critical challenge within the Dafne+ platform and across NFT marketplaces.⁷ Dafne+ sought to operationalise licensing through NFTs within an open environment where tokens could be advertised and resold outside the platform. However, the legal separation between the token and the underlying work complicated such approach. Current industry practice, embedding licenses in platform T&Cs or executing them through individual contractual agreements, remained inadequate.⁸ Such licenses do not attach to the NFT itself, but rather only apply to the original transaction or platform on which they are executed. Consequently, these approaches fail to ensure that all downstream purchasers receive the same rights or obligations.

In response to these challenges, the Token Bound License model was identified as a promising innovation.⁹ Adopting a “public conditional” model, the license applies to the public at large but is exercisable only by NFT owners.¹⁰ By tethering the licensed rights directly to the token, it can ensure the transparent and automatic transfer of rights across each NFT sale. Implementation of the Token Bound license in NFT platforms and marketplaces could thereby offer a novel framework to standardise and clarify licensing of NFTs' linked assets throughout their entire lifecycle, enhancing legal certainty for buyers and sellers. Despite its advantages, technical barriers prevented implementation of the Token Bound License within Dafne+. The model relies on EIP-5218¹¹, an interface designed for ERC-721¹² tokens, which assumes a one-to-one relationship between a token and an NFT. Dafne+ however employs ERC-1155¹³ tokens to enable limited

editions and reduce gas fees, rendering direct integration unfeasible and requiring the development of a new framework inheriting the Token Bound’s core principles and ideas.

Given such limitation, Dafne+ adopted the Creative Commons (CC) PL 4.0 licensing framework.¹⁴ CC licenses offer a standardised and publicly available license with clear versioning, addressing the issues raised by custom licensing and potential compatibility concerns for derivative works. They additionally can clarify licensing conditions in an NFT’s linked work in a simple, legally-valid and reliable manner which covers all downstream sales. However, CC licensing effectively renders NFT ownership redundant for licensing purposes, as NFT buyers receive the same rights as the general public.

Platform Regulation

A further challenge encountered in the Dafne+ project concerned regulatory uncertainty regarding the legal classification of NFT platforms and application of platform regulation rules.¹⁵ These uncertainties stem primarily from unclear definitions and limited regulatory guidance, which ultimately create significant barriers to compliance for operators. Ambiguity persists concerning the classification of NFT platforms under the e-Commerce Directive (ECD)¹⁶, Data Governance Act (DGA)¹⁷, and Digital Services Act (DSA)¹⁸, as well as the applicability of the Copyright in the Digital Single Market (CDSM)¹⁹ Directive’s and DSA’s liability regimes.

Scholarship generally suggests that NFT platforms such as Dafne+ would likely qualify as hosting service providers benefiting from the DSA’s liability safe harbour²⁰, however further clarification from legislators is required on several key points. The scope and exclusions of the Article 2(6) CDSM should be further expanded on, to clarify whether NFT platforms would be subject to the Art 17 CDSM liability regime. Guidance should additionally be provided on the applicability of the DSA safe harbours to NFT platforms. Finally, legislators should clarify what services are to be deemed “copyright intermediaries” excluded from the DGA rules. Such measures would enhance legal certainty for NFT platforms alongside other emerging digital services with mixed functionalities.

GDPR Compliance

A final core issue encountered during the project stemmed from the inherent tension between the nature and features of blockchain technology and the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).²¹ Two types of potential personal data were identified in Dafne+ and blockchain more generally: transactional data and public keys.²² The decentralised and immutable nature of blockchain starkly conflicts with the centralised notion of controllership and core GDPR principles of data minimisation, purpose and storage limitation, and right to rectification and erasure.²³ GDPR compliance is more readily achievable within permissioned or multi-layered blockchain systems, such as Dafne+, where participation is governed by a central entity capable of assuming controllership responsibilities. To ensure alignment with GDPR processing principles and data subjects rights, platform operators should furthermore prioritise off-chain storage of all personal data.²⁴ Erasure of public keys however remains a contested issue, as off-chain storage cannot be implemented. Further regulatory guidance is needed in regards to technical and organisational measures that may fulfil the right to erasure of public keys.

Conclusion

Ultimately, enhanced clarity regarding NFT ownership, implementation of standardised and legally sound licensing mechanisms, and the elimination of uncertainties within applicable regulatory frameworks are vital to ensure transparency, compliance, and long-term sustainability of NFT platforms and ecosystems.

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